

COMMUNITY PERCEPTION OF HUMAN-PRIMATE CONFLICT RESOLUTION IN OKOMU NATIONAL PARK, EDO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to examine community's perception of human-primate conflicts resolution in Okomu National Park, Nigeria. The selected communities include; AT&P, Ugolo, Iguowan, and Iguafole community. Data for the study were collected via semi-structured questionnaire which were randomly distributed to capture information on conflicts between humans and non-human primates as well as their perception towards conflict resolution efforts. A total of one hundred and twenty copies of questionnaire (120) were distributed among farmers, hunters, and other members of the four communities. The data was analyzed using statistical package for Social Scientist (SPSS'23). Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize the data, while inferential techniques were used to test hypotheses. Crop raiding was revealed as the prevalent form of human-primate conflict in the study area. Other factors such as Gender, occupation, accessibility to park and visit frequency influenced perception significantly. Conservation efforts in Okomu park remains hindered as a result of primates-communal clashes over land use and overlap of resources. However, most of the respondents are willing to support primate conservation if there are more community engagement, improved conflict resolution strategies as well as provision of alternative livelihoods to cushion the effect of any damage to properties by wildlife. Addressing these conflicts through participatory conservation approaches and stronger enforcement of conservation laws is essential for preserving the ecological integrity of the park and its primate populations. The study recommends improved participatory approaches towards conflict resolution strategies. This will reduce tensions between local communities, biodiversity and the park management due to the overlap of resources.

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INTRODUCTION

The increasing human population around Okomu National Park has attracted the attention of the park officials, foresters and other relevant stakeholders in the recent time. This population increase has a great pressure on the land, leading to crop raiding by primates, which causes economic losses for local farmers (Hanson, 2022). Such incidents provoke retaliatory actions, such as setting of traps or hunting of primates, which further threatens their survival. These human-wildlife conflicts is seen in similar clashes in other parts of Africa, Asia, and Latin America, where protected areas are encroached upon by human settlements (Linder *et al.*, 2021). Hence, there is a need for the park management to find a way to balance the needs of the local communities while also conserving primate species and other wildlife in the park. Engagement of local communities in conservation efforts is crucial, ensuring that they understand the importance of preserving biodiversity while addressing their livelihood needs. Participatory conservation techniques, which includes involving local community in decision-making process also helps in conflict resolution and enhances sustainability (Bruner *et al.*, 2001). Primate conservation in, and around Okomu National Park faces significant challenges, such as habitat destruction and human-wildlife conflicts (Ogunjemite, 2011). Akinsorotan *et al.* (2021), established that human-wildlife conflicts is of significant impact in Okomu National Park, Nigeria; the study further revealed monkey (primate) to be of great problem in the communities surrounding the park.

Hence, this study provides information on the existing conflicts between primates and community members of Okomu National Park, the causes of such conflict, as well as their perception towards resolving the existing conflicts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Okomu National Park in Edo State, Nigeria occupies an area of 202.24km² in Ovia Southwest Local Government Area of the State. The park lies between 5° 9' and 5° 23' East longitude and latitudes 6° 15' and 6° 25' north, it is appropriately 60 kilometers Northwest of Benin City (Digun-Aweto *et al.*, 2015). Okomu National Park is known for its rich biodiversity, including a wide range of flora and fauna species. The climate of Okomu is tropical with a distinct rainy and dry seasons, it is characterized with high relative humidity throughout the year, and a mean monthly temperature of an average of 30.2⁰C (Olaniyi, 2018).

Figure 1: Map showing Okomu National Park and its Surrounding Communities

Source: Okomu National Park, 2024

Study Design and Sampling Technique

The study was carried out between June 2024 and August 2024. The selected communities include; AT&P, Ugolo, Iguowan, and Iguafole community. The communities were selected based on their proximity to the park. Data for the study were collected via semi-structured questionnaires which were randomly distributed to capture information on conflicts between humans and non-human primates as well as their perception towards conflict resolution efforts. A total of one hundred and twenty copies of questionnaire (120) were distributed among farmers, hunters, and other members of the four communities; with thirty copies of the questionnaires distributed and retrieved in each community.

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using statistical package for Social Scientist (SPSS'23). Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize the data and results were presented using tables and charts; while inferential techniques such as chi-square tests were used to test hypotheses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

The research revealed a higher proportion of males (59.2%), with most of the respondents between ages 36 and 55 years old (35%), this indicates a matured population with the likelihood of experience of human-wildlife conflicts. The predominant occupation among the respondents is farming (41.6%), revealing the

rural and agricultural nature of the area. A significant number of the respondent were married (83.3%), showing the value of family structures in the community. Primary Education (46.7%) is the highest educational attainment, this also indicates an average range of literary level. Most of the respondents were non-indigenes (61.7%), with a household size of 6-10 (50%), and most had never visited the core zone of the park (67.5%) as seen in table 1 below.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (120)	PERCENTAGE (100%)
Gender		
Male	71	59.2
Female	49	40.8
Age		
18-25	7	5.8
26-35	24	20.0
36-45	42	35.0
46-55	40	33.3
56 and above	7	5.8
Occupation		
Farmer	50	41.6
Hunter	29	24.2
Trader	27	22.5
Civil servant	2	1.7
Unemployed	2	1.7
Others	10	8.3
Marital status		
Single	17	14.2
Married	100	83.3
Divorced	2	1.7
Widowed	1	0.8
Education		
No Education	6	5.0
Primary	56	46.7
Secondary	49	40.8
Tertiary	9	7.5
Household size		
1-5	56	46.7
6-10	60	50.0
11-15	4	3.3
Nativity		

Indigene	46	38.3
Non-indigene	74	61.7
Income		
<#30k	11	9.2
#30k-#50k	50	41.7
#50k-#100k	43	35.8
#100k-#200k	15	12.5
>#200k	1	0.8
Year of Residency		
>1yr	7	5.8
1-5yr	33	27.5
6-10	21	17.5
<10yr	37	30.8
Since birth	22	18.3
Distance		
>1km	1	0.8
1-5km	72	60.0
6-10km	20	16.7
<10km	27	22.5
Visit frequency		
Weekly	5	4.2
Monthly	11	9.2
Yearly	23	19.2
Never visited	81	67.5

Human-Primate Conflicts and Communal Clashes

Figure 2 showed that 54% of respondents had experienced Human-Primate conflicts while (46%) reported otherwise. The types of human-primate conflicts experienced by respondents were revealed in Figure 3. Majority of respondents (73.3%) identified crop raiding as a prevalent human-wildlife conflict type, this is followed by damage to property; such as damage to water taps and household roofs (19.2%) and physical confrontations (1.7%).

There are many reasons for communal clashes in communities, such as competition over resources (11.5%) and economic loss from land disputes (29.3%). Miscommunication between park authorities and local communities was also cited by 59.20% of respondents as a major factor contributing to conflicts (Figure 4).

Figure 2: Respondents’ Experience with Human-Primate Conflicts

Figure 3: Types of Conflicts Experienced by Respondents

Figure 4: Reasons for Communal Clashes

Community Perception towards Conflicts Resolution

A significant number of respondents indicates the occurrence of conflict between the community and park authorities as reported in Figure 5, while only 7% did not recognize any controversial issue. This indicates a strong consensus on the existence of conflict.

Strategies for conflicts resolution in the respondents' communities were reported in Figure 6. Interventions by park authorities were the most common methods (60.80%), followed by community meetings and mediation by local leaders (35.0%) and legal action (3.3%).

The result on effectiveness of conflict resolution strategies showed that 56.7% of the respondents find these strategies effective, with 20.8% rating them as somewhat effective and 16.7% deeming not effective (Figure 7). The preferred methods for improving conflict resolution efforts were reported in Figure 8; the figure showed that 56.7% of the respondents advocated for better communication, while 27.5% favored increased community participation and 7.5% supported the distribution of adequate incentives. The suggestions for improving primate conservation and reducing communal clashes is as shown in Figure 9; about 44.2% advocated for increased awareness while 36.7% suggested distribution of incentives to community members.

Figure 5: Perception on the occurrence of Conflict between the Communities and Park Authorities

Figure 6: Strategies for Conflicts Resolution in Respondents' Communities

Figure 7: Perception of Effectiveness of Conflict Resolution Strategies

Figure 8: Perception of the Method that Improves Conflict Resolution Efforts

Figure 9: Suggestions for Improving Primate Conservation and reducing Human-Primate Conflicts in the Park

Relationship between Demographic Information and Community Awareness of Primate Species

Table 2 showed the result on the relationship between demographic information and community awareness of primate species. The result revealed that distance to park has a significant relationship with community awareness, with a P-value of 0.000. This implies that the people living closer to the park are more likely to be aware of primate species within the park.

However, other demographic factors shown in Table 2 have p-values greater than 0.05, which indicate that they do not significantly influence community awareness of primate species and primate conservation within the park.

Table 2: Relationship between the Demographic Information and the Community Awareness of Primate Species

Variable	Chi-Square (X) value	P-value	Remark
Gender	2.880	0.090	Not Significant
Age	4.616	0.329	Not Significant
Occupation	1.024	0.906	Not Significant
Marital status	1.487	0.685	Not Significant
Level of education	4.099	0.251	Not Significant
Household size	1.452	0.484	Not Significant
Origin	1.827	0.401	Not Significant
Income	4.453	0.348	Not Significant
Year of Residency	9.902	0.420	Not Significant
Distance to Park	36.289	0.000	Significant
Visit Frequency	3.286	0.350	Not Significant

$P \leq 0.05$ = Significant, $P > 0.05$ = Not Significant

Relationship between Demographic Information and Community Perception towards Conflict Resolution in Okomu National Park

The result in Table 3 provided insights into which demographic factors significantly influence community perceptions towards conflict resolution in Okomu National Park. Notably, gender has a p-value of 0.000, which indicates a significant relationship with perception of conflict resolution. Similarly, distance to park also showed a significant relationship with a p-value of 0.000, which implies that proximity to the park influences community perception.

In contrast, other variables such as age (p-value = 0.437), occupation (p-value = 0.011), marital status (p-value = 0.249), level of education (P-value = 0.202), etc. showed varying levels of significance. While occupation, year of residency, and visit frequency ($P \leq 0.05$) are significant, other demographic factors do not significantly influence community perceptions of conflict resolution.

Table 3: Relationship between Demographic Information and Community Perception towards Conflict Resolution in Okomu National Park

Variable	Chi-Square (X) value	P-value	Remark
Gender	33.845	0.000	Significant
Age	40.759	0.437	Not Significant
Occupation	63.444	0.011	Significant
Marital status	34.821	0.249	Not Significant
Level of education	36.202	0.202	Not Significant
Household size	21.503	0.368	Not Significant
Origin	18.613	0.547	Not Significant
Income	45.903	0.241	Not Significant
Year of Residency	86.360	0.000	Significant
Distance to Park	95.992	0.000	Significant
Visit Frequency	48.964	0.016	Significant

Discussions

Findings from the study revealed that most of the respondents in the community were males. This agrees with the findings of Alhassan (2010), who noted that most forest dwellers in Ghana were males. This could be due to the traditional gender roles in rural settings where men were more involved in outdoor activities like farming and hunting, this as well increases their interaction with wildlife. The age range of 36 to 55 years shows that the respondents are matured and in their agile years, this agrees with the findings of Amoo *et al.* (2025), that most of the respondents in the communities around Okomu National Park are usually in this age brackets, and they contribute significantly to agricultural productivity. The fact that most of the respondent are into farming activities as their source of livelihood aligns with studies by O'Brien and Wilson (2018), which revealed that members of rural communities rely heavily on farming as their means of sustenance. However, this dependency on farming by rural members greatly explain the reason behind the conflicts existing between agricultural expansion and wildlife conservation efforts. Non-Indigenous residents dominate the study area showing the migratory nature of the population as opined by Zhao *et al.* (2020), that migration influences cultural practices that are related to conservation and land use, thereby each individual might have different attitudes and perception towards biodiversity conservation. There is a gap in community engagement with the park as revealed in the number of respondents who had never

visited the core zone of the park, this is similar to findings by Charnley *et al.* (2014) that physical proximity to protected areas does not always equate to active participation in conservation activities.

The study further revealed the existence of human-primate conflicts in the form of crop raiding as reported by Akinsorotan *et al.* (2021), which documented similar patterns in rural communities of Okomu National Park, Nigeria. This crop raiding by primates leads to huge financial losses to farmers, thereby arousing anger towards wildlife and invariably affecting their attitude and response to primate conservation. This causes farmers to prioritize their source of livelihoods more than wildlife conservation. Miscommunication between park management and community members plays a significant role in communal clashes related to conservation activities as opined by Redpath *et al.* (2013), that poor communication create tensions between conservation stakeholders and locals, giving rise to escalated conflicts. The role of local leaders and community meetings in conflict resolution is seen to be moderately effective, which agrees with findings from Berkes (2004), who argued that community-driven approaches are more effective for resolving conservation conflicts. Although most respondent agrees with the existing conflict resolution strategies in place (Intervention by park authorities), they also desire better communication as a means of resolving conflicts between humans and primates. This is consistent with the studies by Ladan (2014), who pinpointed the importance of reforming conflict resolution mechanisms in protected areas and addressing the main causes of disputes. Better communication between park management and community members will therefore prevent further misunderstandings that could lead to conflicts. With proper awareness and the provision of economic incentives, most of the respondent shows readiness to participate in conservation activities, reflecting a positive response towards wildlife and habitat protection. This agrees with the study of Nelson and Morris (2021), that there will be increase in community participation once there is provision of economic incentives such as a means of alternative livelihoods, thereby reducing human-wildlife conflicts.

The study further reveals that proximity to the park increases awareness of primate conservation among community members as stated by Scholte and De Groot (2010), who found out that proximity to protected areas often increases awareness and interactions with wildlife. Demographic factors such as age and level of education did not significantly affect community awareness and perception as opposed to the study of Borresen *et al.* (2023), which reported the positive effect of education in the appreciation of nature and that factors such as respondent's education can play a more significant role in shaping attitude towards conservation.

CONCLUSION

Human-wildlife conflicts continue to be a major issue of concern as it continues to create tension between the park authorities and local communities. Furthermore, the study revealed that while community members

recognize the need for primate conservation, miscommunication and ineffective conflict resolution strategies increases conflicts and cases of communal clashes. However, there is a great potential for improvement as most of the community members expressed willingness to participate in conservation activities and conflicts resolution, as much as there is improved communication and incentives in place.

Recommendation

The management of Okomu National Park should improve on their communication and conflict resolution strategies to reduce the misunderstandings between park authorities and community members. There should be more awareness campaigns to educate the locals on the benefits of primate conservation and wildlife management. Also, community engagement should be enhanced through participatory approaches, allowing local residents to contribute to decision-making processes in conservation efforts. Workshops and programs on alternative means of livelihoods should be introduced to community members so as to reduce their dependence on activities that harm primates and their habitats, such as farming on wild lands and illegal hunting of wildlife.

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Conflicts of Interest

There exists no conflict of interest.

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